

Ecological Bond of Trees and Characters from the English Renditions of Kalki's *Ponniyin Selvan*

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Abstract

Trees are seen as the universal symbol of life in literature. The relation of the trees to the humans and vice-versa form an important web of sustainability. Kalki Krishnamurthy's Ponniyin Selvan, the classic novel vibrantly holds this view. There are numerous depictions of trees in the novel having bondage with the characters. The paper tries to decipher the ecological bond between the characters with the trees. The depiction of ecology in Kalki Krishnamurthy's "Ponniyin Selvan" would enable better comprehension of the scientific theories of human survival and the evolution of intelligent species with admirable character traits. The concept of trees used in the novel is remarkable. The unsurpassable use of the images of nature employed in the work gives testimony to the author's strong bond with nature. It portrays the Tamil sense and culture at the pinnacle of the Chozla Empire. The paper also analyses how Kalki Krishnamurthy has connected the characters Prince Arulmozli, Lord Pazluvoor, Vandiya Devan, Thirumalai Nambi Azlvar-adiyan, Sendan Amudan and Kundavai to trees. Kalki employs trees as symbols to convey the significant characteristic traits of principal characters in "Ponniyin Selvan" such as Arulmozli's magnanimity, Lord Pazluvoor's sacrifice and martyrdom, Vandiya Devan's aesthetic admiration and love, Nambi's spirituality, Sendan Amudan's pious graciousness and Kundavai's nobility. All these aspects are conveyed to the readers by relating the characters to various species of trees. Hence, the article investigates the bond between the trees and the characters of "Ponniyin Selvan".

Keywords: Ecological Bond, Trees, Characters, English Renditions, Kalki's *Ponniyin Selvan*.

Introduction

The bond between the trees and humans dates back to the origin of life. The relation of humans to their environment, especially trees triggered the evolution from the caves to civilization. This idea is backed by scientific evidence as well. The source of oxygen for living creatures is contributed by trees. There are lots of works abounding with ecological consciousness and provide a fertile ground to assess the strength of the bond of human with their environment. Tonic points out;

Eco-criticism is emphasized on the relation between human beings and environment in literature, the term of ecology or eco-criticism came from the combination of science, the physical environment and spiritual to the aim of protect and serve human beings and we can say eco-criticism is a way that human beings fight to survival in this world. (43-44)

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By employing the concept of ecology and literature, it would enable a clear comprehensive relationship between the life of humans and their relation with nature. It will also elucidate the evolution of the spiritual self in humans. Kalki's *Ponniyin Selvan* has such characters who are bound with trees. The noble characteristic traits such as the magnanimity of Arulmozhi, the sacrifice of Lord Pazluvoor, the aesthetic sense of Vandiya Devan, the spirituality of Nambi, the courteousness of Sendan Amudan, the nobility and compassion of Kundavai are brought under the scan of eco-criticism. The study points out the characters' relationship to the nature of trees as portrayed in Kalki's *Ponniyin Selvan*.

Objective

1. To study the role of nature in human life and experience as reflected in the novel.
2. To understand the connection between nature and human interaction.
3. To decipher the myriad phases of bonding with nature by the characters of the novel.
4. To examine the significance of the influence of nature on the characters.
5. To establish harmony with nature is the nobility of man.

Methodology

It is a descriptive study employing the idea of the significance of nature in the lives of characters in the novel. Nature and human bonding have myriad layers of relationships which have been explored by deciphering how the characters connect themselves to nature. The work chosen for the study, *Ponniyin Selvan* authored by Kalki Krishnamurthy is brought under the scan of ecological relations between the characters and trees.

Review of Literature

Murali. S. (1998) in his work "Environmental Aesthetics Interpretation of Nature in "Akam" and "Puram" Poetry" elaborates on the key features employed by the prominent Tamil writers about aspects of the relationship between humans and nature. François Gro (1984) reveals the intensity in which the landscape has been embedded in the works of Sangam literature. He throws light on the various nuances followed by the writers of the period. Uma Ramamoorthy (2021) discusses the significance of the eco-sensibilities employed by the poets of the Sangam era, she also discusses how the poets related the concepts of geography to the emotions of the characters in the works. Varadarajan, M (1969) presents an analysis of the depiction of nature and the relationship between human emotions and nature. Barry (2018) states the parameters through which the ecocritics can study the works of literature; he has elaborated on the criteria to assess the work of literature. In it, how a literary text has to be assessed stage by stage using the ecocritical theory has been delved deeply. The writers have connected nature with human life has been depicted in a soulful manner. No past studies have focused on Kalki's works from an eco-critical perspective. Hence, this study is novel and becomes vital at the need of time when the entire world experiencing climate change and other ecological problems. Further study will give insights into keeping the individual qualities of the modern man with a love for nature to avoid catastrophic accidents.

The Noble Attributes of Man

The famous quote by Charles Darwin praises the human race for the love upheld by the human species for all living creatures. "The love for all living creatures is the most noble attribute of man" – Charles Darwin. This noblest attribute of humans is the key factor for a human being upholding the power of survival. Right from prehistoric times, humans have

sustained a bond with all living creatures. The bonding of humans with the trees moves back to times immemorial. The idea of trees being observers of the characters has been employed through literature. Tamil culture also advocates the rapport between nature and man is an important virtue of life.

The images of the trees in the ancient scribbling on the rocks, sculpting, painting and rituals are concrete evidence for the trees being the source of creative inspiration among writers. Trees are viewed as strong elements that contribute to the sustainability of life. The nature and environment influence humans and vice versa. Kalki Krishnamurthy, the legendary Tamil writer is noted for his regard for nature, his fictional passages in the epic novel *Ponniyin Selvan* surpass poetry when he describes nature. His novel has rich content that possesses the aesthetic and scientific views of the elements of nature. The references to the magnificent trees are plentiful in Kalki's *Ponniyin Selvan*, they act as significant characters themselves in the work. The significance of the trees in the work is touchstoned with specific reference to eco-critical ideas. Kalki has created his characters Arulmozli, Lord Pazluvoor, Vandiya Devan, Thirumalai Nambi Azlvar-adiyan, Sendan Amudan and Kundavai close to nature, in particular with trees.

The Law of Life

Kalki Krishnamurthy foregrounds nature as a prominent subject matter in *Ponniyin Selvan*, the title of the work itself gives testimony to the claim. The inseparable bonding of human life with nature, green life is the unwritten law of nature. *Ponniyin Selvan* is filled with a lot of depictions of nature. Peter Barry insists that 'nature writing' concerns the two middle ones – 'the scenic sublime' and 'the country side' (Barry 256). Kalki Krishnamurthy's *Ponniyin Selvan* is abundant with the aspects of the ancient city and village lifestyle and the sublime beauty of the native land. Peter Barry holds the view that ecocritics assess literary works based on certain parameters.

They re-read major literary works from an ecocentric perspective, with particular attention to the representation of the natural world. They extend the applicability of a range of ecocentric concepts, using them of things other than the natural world-concepts such as growth and energy, balance and imbalance, symbiosis and mutuality, and sustainable or unsustainable uses of energy and resources. They give special canonical emphasis to writers who foreground nature as a major part of their subject matter. (Barry 269)

The views of Peter Barry are relatable to the work of *Ponniyin Selvan*. The novelist has merged nature with the plot and structure of the novel. The novelist has spun human emotions and aspirations in connection with nature. In various instances, the characters construct an emotional bridge with trees in their environment.

The Source of Life

The title of the work *Ponniyin Selvan* refers to the prominent character, Raja Raja Chozlan (Arulmozli), who has a strong connection with the River Cauvery, referred to as Ponni Nathi in the work. As a child, *Ponniyin Selvan* accidentally fell into the river during his journey and was luckily saved due to the timely interference of a kind-hearted brave lady who saved him from drowning. This incident earns him the name of *Ponniyin Selvan*, meaning the cherished child of River Cauvery. The banks of Cauvery are adorned by nature

by lustrous trees. A fine Ecosystem existed in the river bank due to the presence of the trees. Kalki wrote it in Tamil; the translator Neelameggham translates it as;

Look at those luscious groves of trees on the Cauvery bank. How big are the fruits hanging from the trunk and branches of the jack-tree! There is nothing like this in the dry Thondai region! Look at those monkeys gathered in these fertile lands. How delightful to see them jump from tree to tree! I remember the descriptions in Gnana-sambanda's poems: Maidens dance on the stages set in the street-corners of Thiru-vai-ar. Song and music accompany that dance with melodious drumbeats; Monkeys hearing those drums (mattalam) think that the skies are thundering with an approaching storm: they climb to the top of palm trees and look up at the skies waiting for the rains! (Neelameggham (trans), New Floods 102)

One should not think that it is mere imagination. Kalki researched the culverts and bronze plates from the temples built by Raja Raja. The ancient Tamils gave more importance to nature and preserved it intelligently. Still, many places are lush with certain trees as per the documentation.

Kalki Krishnamurthy narrates the legendary tale of the origin of Cauvery, in the most romantic terms possible. The science behind the branching out of the river and the pattern of natural irrigation for the abundant vegetation of the region has been focused, on employing romantic expressions. Even the author falls short of words when he desires to describe the *Kadamba* and *Punnai* trees that adorn the banks of the river. The fertility these trees bring to the land is beyond description. It will mesmerize all in a trance.

River Ponni, born and raised in the Kudagu Hills, after her childhood was past, wished to meet the Ocean King, her chosen husband. She went swiftly, crossing hill and dale, rocky mountain and canyon. As she came closer and closer, the joyous anticipation of meeting her beloved Lord, the Ocean King, made her thrive and grow. She went even further. Two arms grew to embrace the lover. Spreading her arms wide, she leaped and surged forward. Two arms were not sufficient for her ardent enthusiasm. Her loving arms grew into ten, twenty, hundred! Stretching out all these arms in eagerness she neared the Ocean King. She was the bride meeting her beloved. Chozla women, her bridesmaids, dressed her in such wondrous ways. They clothed her in the beautiful greens of rice-fields. They decorated her with colorful flowers; and showered her with fragrant woods. How can we describe the enchanting kadamba and punnai trees on both her banks: they covered her with pearls and rubies of flowers. (Neelameggham (trans), New Floods 46)

Similarly, the connections of the characters with nature are widely seen in this outstanding work. It depicts nature in all of its diverse forms, such as serene and turbulent, creative and destructive. "Everything is connected to everything else" (Commoner 16). In many instances, Kalki highlights the importance of trees and forests. Worshipping of trees and forests is a native tradition in Tamil culture. Shiva points out that in India forests are revered.

Forests have always been central to Indian civilization. They have been worshipped as Aranyani, the Goddess of the Forest, the primary source of life and fertility, and the forest as a community has been viewed as a model for

societal and civilizational evolution. The diversity, harmony and the self-sustaining nature of the forest formed the organizational principles guiding Indian civilization; the Aranyana Sanskriti (roughly translatable as ‘the culture of the forest’ or ‘forest culture’) was not a condition of primitiveness, but one of conscious choice. (Shiva 53)

The narrative pattern in the work has a high concentration on the elements of nature. It provides evidence of the daily interactive patterns of humans with nature. The exploitation of nature or greedy abuse scenario prevalent in the current scenario was absent during ancient times. Kalki’s narration gives testimony to the communion of humans with nature. The references to trees in the work are abundant. His work highlights the importance of the cultural and ecological significance of the trees. Kalki’s works are milestones of the craftsmanship of Tamil writers.

Arulmozli’s Enlightenment and Sacrifice

Arulmozli during his stay in the Buddhist monastery observes the lives of the monks, the serenity and the association of the monks with nature inspire him. The statue of Buddha meditating under the Bodhi tree is a strong metaphor used by Kalki to bring forth the heightened influence of trees on human life and history. The Bodhi tree is viewed as a sacred symbol of wisdom; attributing it to the fact that Lord Buddha attained enlightenment under the Bodhi tree.

Lord Buddha sat under the Bodhi tree a great revelation came on him. The way to remove the sufferings of people was revealed to him at that time. It was only from then on did Buddha start preaching people about life and suffering. (Rengasamy (trans), *The Supreme Sacrifice* 821)

Arulmozli tries to provide a logical notion to the idea of Buddha’s enlightenment. Buddha on viewing the suffering of the ordinary people mediated to find a cure for their suffering. Through meditation, he was able to identify that the “desire is the root cause of sorrow”, hence he preached abdicating the worldly desires to attain peace and happiness. This interaction with the Buddhist monk acts as a preface to the magnanimous offer of Arulmozli’s sacrifice of his rightful throne to Senthan Amuthan, who has a claim to the throne based on the bloodline of the kingdom.

Lord Pazluvoor and Sacrifice

Trees are shelters for lovers, travellers and the homeless. Ecology is viewed as a multi-faceted scenario which offers the necessities to humans and other living organisms, such as food, shelter and clothing. Trees are viewed as magnificent entities that witness the life and growth of civilization as silent spectators. The palm tree symbol is carved in the coins of Lord Pazluvoor, signifying his strength and wealth. Lord Pazluvoor acts as the palm tree in strength. He sacrifices himself at last after committing misdeeds against the King’s family. He has an important place in the victories of the Chozla regime. When he dies, Kalki registers his death in comparison to a big tree. Usually, every tree has a unique ecosystem; the birds, insects, creepers and other creatures live over and under them. Lord Pazluvoor as the treasurer of the Chozla empire saved the subjects. When Lord Pazluvoor commits suicide as an act of repentance Kalki refers to it as the demise of a great tree, highlighting the vitality and life energy offered by a colossal tree to other living things. In Karikala’s death mystery, Vandiya Devan’s innocence is proved due to the confession of Lord Pazluvoor. Like the tree,

that provides prosperity to the human and other creatures in the form of wood and manure, Lord Pazluvoor realizes the importance of the Chozla regime and saves Vandiya Devan. Kalki depicts it superbly with reference to a big tree.

Vandiy Devan and Nature

The philosophy of nature contributing to the psychic health of individuals has been prominent in the novel. The references to the thick dense forests, rich in flora and fauna that provide purified air and plentiful resources are seen in the beginning of the work. Vandiya Devan is captivated by the magnanimity of nature, the narration highlights the prosperity of the Chozla land and the vibrant lifestyle of its people because of the fertility of the soil. Vandiya Devan who hails from the Thondai Mandalam is mesmerized by the scenic beauty of the Chozla Kingdom. He states, “**Vallavareyan went towards the Arisalaru River. As he proceeded towards the land of the Cholas, he couldn't help admiring the beauty of his surroundings. There was greenery everywhere! Green fields, trees, crops, small ponds, beautiful lakes and friendly villagers... No wonder the kingdom was so prosperous!**” (Sumeetha Manikandan (trans), *New Floods* 122). Similar to the Sangam poets, Kalki has employed the relation between nature and human emotions. Especially, when he describes the meeting of Vandiya Devan and Kundavai, he resorts to connecting nature with the emotions of the individual. Vandiya Devan meets his beloved Kundavai and is captivated by her beauty. The novelist here employs the symbol of a beautiful creeper and bright butterfly to relate the romantic connection between the Thalaivan (lover) and Talaivi (beloved) as similar to the portrayal of romantic love in Sangam literature. Kalki writes;

A beautiful creeper tree with slender vines stood between them. A bright, lovely butterfly flew in and sat on the vine, distracting Kundavai's attention. But Vandiya Devan seemed transfixed by the beautiful visage of Kundavai's face. He did not look at the butterfly nor did he note his surroundings. (Neelamegham (trans), *New Floods* 348)

The fertility of the Chozla land with rich flora and fauna is depicted in this episode, wherein nature becomes an active character in the lives of humans. Uma Ramamoorthy appreciates the effective employment of nature to describe the emotions of individuals and the strong connections humans have shared with nature from ancient times.

The geographic control of life is an idea recently reached by science and newly expounded in treaties on Anthropogeography. But the ancient Tamil poets have somehow understood the influence of universal bodies on natural environment and in turn on man and have established conventions in their works especially on various aspects of life. Love is the most established theme of “Akam” poems and so Nature has a vital role in the lives of the hero and the heroine. The convention of using the theme of influence of Natural world on man proves that ancient Tamil poets were inspired by acute details of Nature and their influence on human life in its different aspects. Thus, the literary conventions of the age are seen not only in such gracious blending of the human passions with the beauties of Nature but also in the classification of the sentiments of love in accordance with the different regions and assigning them to particular seasons and hours. (Uma 91)

Uma highlights the integral bond among the three prominent factors of life such as nature, humans and universal connection as seen in Sangam Poetry.

Nambi's Bond with Trees

Kalki Krishnamurthy highlights the ambience of serenity and protection offered by trees. "Azlvar-adiyan and Vandiya Devan sat down under a large banyan tree on the river bank. Several kinds of birds roosting in the thick, leafy branches of that wide-spreading, large tree raised a pleasing musical sound (Neelameggham, New Floods 62)". The interaction of the characters with nature provides them solace and peace of mind. In several incidents, the characters find peaceful hearts in turbulent situations by developing communion with trees. Kalki writes about Nambi in the forest.

He heard a noise above his head: looked up. Some small animal -- lizard or squirrel jumped to a different branch. A small patch of the clear sky could be seen through the branches of the tree. Stars twinkled and peeped down. In that silent, dark forest the stars seemed to extend a friendly smile towards him. Therefore, Thirumalai Nambi Azlvar-adiyan looked up at the stars and started talking softly... (Neelameggham (Trans), New Floods 94)

Nambi develops a natural bond with nature and begins his self-narration, feeling safe in the arms of nature. Here, the state of Nambi is similar to that of the birds that seek abode for the night, when migrating to different landscapes.

Sendan Amudan

Kalki Krishnamurthy highlights the meeting of Vandiya Devan and Sendan Amudan, an ardent devotee of Lord Shiva in comparison to the tall *Konnai* trees. It serves as a strong symbol to represent the quality of Sendan Amudan who admires nature and lives in the orchard. The significance of the flowers of trees in the devotional practices is highlighted through the incident.

On hearing the song, Vandiya Devan opened his eyes and looked out. Outside, in the garden he saw tall konnai trees (the Bignonia family) draped with wreaths of golden yellow flowers! Sendan Amudan held a large flower tote in one hand and a long bamboo pole in the other. While he sang, his hands plucked the yellow flowers with the harvest pole. He appeared neatly dressed, having risen, and bathed early, his forehead was adorned with broad ashen marks making him appear like another ever youthful Markandeya, that ardent devotee of Shiva. (Neelameggham (trans), New Floods 117)

Like the youthful, Markandeya, the trees retain their youth all through their life. They mature in a slow pattern, which enables them to witness the massive movement of time and the alteration of civilization. Sendan lives in the orchard and spends his with the foster parents life knitting flowers to the gods.

Compassion of Kundavai

Kundavai's concern for fellow human beings has been depicted in several instances in the novel. Despite being a powerful princess, she exhibits her intrinsic nobility by giving directions to the charioteer to wait under the shade of the banyan tree. Trees have been the source of solace for the downtrodden, who seek the aid of these trees. Kundavai is a keen observer of nature who relates the phenomenon of nature to the emotional turbulences among

humans. Vanathi considers herself inferior to her love interest Arulmozli, who is noted for his valour and intelligence. Kundavai says;

“Why not? Haven’t you seen the mist covering the sun in the morning?” Hearing this, Vanathi suddenly became enthusiastic, “So you really think that the mist can attain the sun’s affection?” But again, her happiness evaporated. “The mist wishes to gain the sun’s attention but what does the sun do - it burns so fiercely that the mist disappears.” “That is wrong, Vanathi. Knowing the mists’ desire the sun absorbs her within himself. The sun is so possessive about the mist that it does not want anybody to look at her in the daylight.” (Pavitra & Varsha (Trans) 99)

Kundavai cites the example of the unity of the mist with the Sun rays, romantically and tries to convince Vanathi that Arulmozli would value her as his most precious treasure, which he would hold dear to his life. Hence, Kundavai acts as the catalyst to strengthen the bonding love between Arulmozli and Vanathi. Kundavai states,

The Bond between Trees and Humans

Kalki Krishnamurthy highlights the unique quality of trees of unconditional love, impartial generosity and power of re-emergence. The reciprocity of nature to the affection of humans has also been recorded in several instances. Trees provide shelter to a wide range of living creatures; they create and maintain a unique ecosystem of their own on their branches and under their shade. The songs of the birds are testimony to their serene existence. Similarly, the mentality of humans to enjoy the tranquillity of nature and the songs of the birds are used as parallels with the incidents of peace and turmoil in the work.

What can we say about the sweetness of the song they sang? Even the water in the river seemed to be still as it listened to their melodious music. Even the cuckoos and parrots on the trees listened quietly. We humans, blessed with the fortune of being able to listen, why should we not be enchanted by their song? (Neelameggham (trans), New Floods 46)

Humans during the primeval times, lived in harmony with nature, the creatures of the wild nature correlated with their human brothers. The tribal communities even today can retain their bonding with the wild creatures. Their understanding of nature surpasses advanced scientific knowledge at times. Due to the emergence of the acquisitive attitude of humans, they tend to mislay their bonding with nature, which is vital for the survival of life on earth. Harrison comments on the need to understand the role of humans in the ecological space.

Rather than turn to romanticism as a guide to current environment practices, our interest is in romanticism as a site for the emergence of eco poetics and as a discourse that opens up critical questions and lines of investigation about our human place in the life world. (Harrison 2)

Kalki Krishnamurthy’s *Ponniyin Selvan*, celebrated as a historical fiction, beyond doubt would qualify as an impressive work on ecology and human bonding with nature. It discourses the role of human life amidst nature and the role of nature in humans.

Conclusion

The relation between humans and trees is depicted profoundly in Kalki Krishnamurthy’s *Ponniyin Selvan*, aligning with the idea of ecology. How the characters

relate to their environment and the symbolic significance of their interaction have been examined through the eco-critical lens and the claims have been logically justified. Arulmozli's magnanimity is linked to the idea of Buddha's abdication of his throne, followed by his enlightenment under the Bodhi tree. The supreme sacrifice of the throne by Arulmozli is linked to his stronghold on the high philosophy of contentment like the trees. He remained a philosopher prince and kind in his life. Kalki has related the strength and uses of the palm tree to Lord Pazluvoor, the legendary war hero, who sacrifices his life to save the innocent Vandiya Devan from death and sacrifices him for righteousness. Vandiya Devan's aesthetic admiration towards nature and his quest to be in the company of nature is related to the close encounters with the Chozla people that he enjoys in the company of nature at all his missions. Kalki employs the bonding between the elements of nature to signify the romantic love between Vandiya Devan and Kundavai. Their love flourishes like nature which cannot be curtailed by human power. Nambi's spirituality is represented through his correlation with nature. He enjoys divine peace and serenity in the company of nature. The austere priest enjoys tranquillity and blends in with the tune of nature. Sendan Amudan's pious graciousness and inherit nobility are linked to his connection with nature. He feels joy in preparing garlands for his Lord and does this with utmost love, care and joy. The depiction of Sendan Amudan as Markandeya holds good since he holds on to the divine as his master and Lord. Kundavai's nobility is revealed by her interaction with the other characters in the novel. She like the banyan tree tries to provide comfort for the needy and the people in distress and tries to rejoin her family members. She becomes the source of support for her family, friends, relatives and dependents. The River Ponni becomes the source of life for the Chozla region, spreading the green carpet of trees for fertility to walk on, the lush green trees on her banks stand as guards, testifying to her power as creator and protector. The various species of trees referred to by Kalki in *Ponniyin Selvan* are significant characters of the ecosphere. By relating these characters with the magnificent trees of nature Kalki has immortalized his work, *Ponniyin Selvan*. In the case of future studies, A detailed study can be done on the novel to extract eco-critical and eco-feminist themes from this novel.

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